

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *There are many attractive things for a child in kindergarten. The study allows us to determine and rank the value preferences of children. The most important thing for children in kindergarten is the opportunity to get involved in different types of children's activities and the availability of a variety of toys and materials for this in kindergarten. Next in importance is the opportunity to communicate with peers. Unfortunately, communication with the teacher is not significant and attractive in the characteristics of the kindergarten through the eyes of children. This fact suggests that educators are not et able to optimally build their relationship with the child. The current stage can be characterized as a time of innovation and change, modernization of domestic education and its integration into the global educational space. This is a period of rapid change of conditions and requirements of the system, a time of flexible, adaptive, initiative and creative teachers.*

Key words: *Technology, ecology, elementary mathematics, labor training, preschool education, psychology, pedagogy.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ВОСПИТАНИЯ И ОБУЧЕНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. *В детском саду для ребенка существует много привлекательного. Исследование позволяет определить и ранжировать ценностные предпочтения детей. Самой значимой для детей в детском саду является возможность включаться в разные виды детской деятельности и наличие для этого в детском саду разнообразных игрушек и материалов. Следующим по значимости выступает возможность общения со сверстниками. К сожалению, общение с воспитателем не является значимым и привлекательным в характеристике детского сада глазами детей. Этот факт заставляет предположить, что воспитателям пока еще не удастся оптимально для ребенка построить свои отношения с ним. Современный этап может быть охарактеризован как время инноваций и перемен, модернизации отечественного образования и его интеграции в мировое образовательное пространство. Это период быстрой смены условий и требований системы, время гибких, адаптивных, инициативных и творческих педагогов.*

Ключевые слова: *Технология, экология, элементарная математика, трудового обучения, дошкольного воспитания, психология, педагогика.*

INTRODUCTION

The legislation on preschool education and upbringing consists of this Law and other legislative acts (The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 16.12.2019 No. ZRU-595)[2].

children with special educational needs are children with individual needs, regardless of whether there is a disability or not, who need special attention from families, teachers, specialists, society and the state;

state preschool educational organization — an organization funded and managed by the state and providing preschool educational and educational services in accordance with the state

standard of preschool education and upbringing;

preschool age — the age of children from birth to seven years old, until the moment of providing him with education in general secondary education organizations;

preschool education and upbringing is a type of continuing education aimed at educating and educating children, their intellectual, spiritual, moral, ethical, aesthetic and physical development, as well as preparing children for general secondary education;

the state standard of preschool education and upbringing is a set of mandatory requirements for the volume, content and quality of the educational process, the construction and equipment of a preschool educational organization, as well as the organization of healthy nutrition and safety of preschool children;

the state educational program of preschool education and upbringing is a document defining the scope and content of basic knowledge, skills and abilities to be acquired by a child, as well as characterizing the specifics of the content of education and upbringing, the specifics of the organization of the educational process;

preschool educational organization is a state and non—state organization that provides educational and educational services in the field of preschool education and upbringing;

a non—governmental preschool educational organization is a legal entity that provides educational and educational services in the field of preschool education and upbringing on the basis of a license to carry out activities in the field of providing non-governmental educational services;

the professional standard of a teacher is a set of basic requirements for personal professional qualities, knowledge, skills and abilities of a teacher of a preschool educational organization;

an alternative form of education and upbringing is a model of the organization of an innovative educational process in the system of preschool education and upbringing.

Among the preferred activities, children distinguish first of all the game. In kindergartens, conditions are created for the inclusion of children in different types of games. At the same time, the study revealed a common problem for all regions — the lack of sufficient time in the pedagogical process to organize independent children's games and meet the gaming needs of children. The main reasons for this are: the dominance of educational activities to the detriment of children's play activities; the use of games to solve only educational tasks or regulate behavior [2].

In a modern kindergarten, a subject environment has been created that arouses the active interest of children. However, the study revealed the fact that there are significant limitations of children in the use of these environmental conditions. A significant and not always justified list of restrictions prevents the formation of the child's subjective position, the manifestation of such qualities as activity, independence, responsibility for the changes made in the group space, for the established order in the group.

Most children love their caregivers. They see a teacher first of all as a teacher, and would like to interact with him as a person with his own views, interests, hobbies and problems. Humane, informal communication with the teacher is not enough for almost every modern child [3].

Evaluation of a kindergarten through the eyes of a child depends more on the specific people working there, on their attitude to children and to their professional duties, on the

personal and professional qualities of the educator.

Preschool childhood is a unique, self—valuable period of personality formation, having a pronounced specificity of age development, requiring special psychological and pedagogical support and conditions.

Preschool childhood is an integral phenomenon, the basis that determines the development of a person throughout his life. The world of children, the world of childhood traditionally attracts the attention of scientists and practitioners who study the patterns of development and formation of a child, developing approaches to his upbringing.

A child is a unique, inimitable, bright personality. His subjectivity and identity are manifested in desires, interests, needs, selective attitude to the world and people, in conflicts and contradictions with himself and others, in independence and creativity in accessible activities[1].

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

A preschool-age child develops by accumulating individual experience, life impressions and at the same time actively transforming culture, bringing elements of his subculture into it, becoming a subject of various types of activity. A preschooler broadcasts our adult world with all its advantages and disadvantages. This is not just a reflection — it is an active work of the senses and mind, understanding the powerful information flow, experiencing everything that he sees and hears around him.

Adults, including adults who have such a difficult and such a wonderful profession as a teacher, are called upon to help the child discover the world for himself and himself — the world!

The current stage can be characterized as a time of innovation and change, modernization of domestic education and its integration into the global educational space. This is a period of rapid change of conditions and requirements of the system, a time of flexible, adaptive, initiative and creative teachers.

The peculiarities of the development of mental processes of a child in preschool childhood are characterized by a number of principles that must be taken into account when designing technologies for the upbringing, training and development of preschoolers, when organizing research on the problems of modern childhood. These include principles such as:

— the creative nature of development, manifested in the generation of signs and symbols by the child, when he already acts as a subject of culture from infancy;

— the leading role of the socio-cultural context of development, which manifests itself in different ways in different periods of childhood and affects the child's mastery of the simplest tools and objects, facial expressions and gestures, the picture of the world, the nature of activity and behavior;

— the special significance of sensitive periods of development (different for different ages), that is, the periods most sensitive to awareness, assimilation and implementation of norms, forms, conditions of human life (language, communication methods, methods of productive activity, etc.);

— joint activity of adults and children as a driving force of child development, transmission to children by adults achievements of historical human development;

— the presence of a leading activity in each age period and the laws of its change as the basis for the continuity of periods of mental development of the child;

— determination of the zone of the nearest development of a growing person. "The zone

of the closest development of a child is the distance between the level of his actual development, determined with the help of tasks solved independently, and the level of possible development, determined with the help of tasks solved under the guidance of adults and in cooperation with smarter comrades" (L. S. Vygotsky);

— amplification (enrichment, expansion, deepening) of children's development as a condition for the child's free search and finding himself in the material, in one form or another of activity and communication;

— an enduring value for the formation of a full-fledged personality at all stages of child development, which does not allow to force the process of a child's transition from one stage of development to the next (for example, from image to word, from play to learning, from objective action to mental, etc.). Each stage must exhaust itself, then it will provide favorable conditions for the transition to a new one, and his achievements will remain for life;

— the principle of unity of affect and intellect, or the principle of an active figure, meaning the formation of consciousness as a result of the joint activity of affective and personal components. Consideration of all mental phenomena through the prism of their origin and formation in activity;

— the mediating role of sign-symbolic structures in the formation of connections between objects and actions;

— internalization and exteriorization as mechanisms of development, meaning the transition from the external to the internal and vice versa;

— uneven and heterochronous development, manifested in the fact that various mental functions, properties and formations develop unevenly, vibrationally and heterogeneously. This principle allows us to explain the individual rate of development of mental processes in a child [6].

The peculiarities of the pedagogical technology of labor education are associated with the construction of a pedagogical process aimed at the integral development of the child as a subject of activity, the creation of conditions for the manifestation of his potential capabilities and abilities, awareness of the importance of the value of labor as he enters the modern world, labor relations with loved ones.

The construction of the pedagogical process based on the methods of interrelation of the means of labor education determines the step-by-step introduction of pupils to the modern world in the process of various children's activities.

The first step in familiarizing with the modern world is the formation of knowledge about the subjects and work of adults (in the younger group — supervision of the manufacture of adult crafts, paper toys, sewing buttons, sewing hats for dolls, etc.; in the middle group — acquaintance with the work of kindergarten staff babysitters, laundresses, cooks; in the older groups — acquaintance with the professions of parents, their interests, hobbies at home — cooking, needlework, etc.) [8].

The second step is related to mastering labor skills, methods of self—control and self-esteem (at a younger age, this is the development of self-service processes; in the middle group, the development of feasible processes of household labor (setting the table for lunch, washing toy dishes); at an older preschool age, you can teach vacuuming, elementary mending of clothes (sew a button, a hanger), cooking the simplest dishes (sandwiches, vinaigrette, salad, juice, etc.).

The third step is connected with the entry of the child into real labor relations with people close to him (educator, nanny, parents). To do this, a special environment is created in the group, taking into account the age, individual sexual interests and inclinations of the pupils. The motivation of younger preschoolers to self-service is stimulated by attractive didactic manuals that help them master the skills of buttoning, lacing, soaping while playing. In the older groups, corners of children's creative work are created, where boys can burn, make from different materials, a designer, and girls can sew, embroider, etc.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Interaction with children at a younger age activates curiosity about the work of adults, encourages initiative and independence of kids in self-service. To do this, it is necessary to emotionally support the child, encouraging him to independently perform individual self-service actions with a satisfactory result with a little help from an adult and peers (tie a scarf from behind, help pull the fur coat off his shoulders). In each individual case, it is necessary to celebrate children's achievements and successes ("How good that you do it yourself", "What a good fellow that you dressed yourself (washed your hands)"), so that the child rejoices in his achievements, strives for recognition of his independence, self-affirmation, praise of adults for their skill.

It is necessary to support the desire of the baby to be neat, to appeal to the elders with a request to help eliminate shortcomings, to teach them to use generally recognized ways of providing and accepting help, to thank with a word, a smile, a gesture. Didactic games and exercises will ensure the development of fine motor skills necessary for self-service actions. The educator also needs to create conditions and encourage children to reflect self-service processes in household-themed games, when a child in the role of a mother teaches "her children" to wash, eat, comb their hair, and monitor their appearance[12].

In the middle group, it is necessary to develop a cognitive interest in the adult world, a desire to enter into natural labor relations through the provision of effective assistance appropriate to childhood. Interaction and cooperation with the child is focused on the development of his cognitive activity and independence in work. It is necessary to promote the familiarization of children with self-service in the process of regime moments in the daily life of the kindergarten. For example, to help fasten the buttons on clothes from behind, to remind that wet things should be taken to the drying cabinet, etc. To cultivate a careful attitude to things, objects and equipment (carefully hang and fold clothes, put soap in a soap dish, carefully turn off the water after washing).

Effective use of game characters that allow children to learn to set goals, choose objects and tools, organize their workplace, perform labor actions in the correct sequence; master special labor skills and ways of self-monitoring the quality of performance. It is important to praise for the manifestations of conscientiousness, responsibility, activity and initiative, the desire to help adults, comrades, get involved in labor affairs, empathize with the failures of the child, rejoice in his successes, let the children feel their skill [10].

In the older group, it is important for the child to provide the experience of entering into natural labor relations with adults and peers in accordance with the increased physical and mental capabilities of children of the sixth year of life.

The inclusion of a child in natural labor relations in kindergarten and family conditions becomes the content of everyday life, allowing you to realize your growing up. Therefore, it is

necessary to expand the range of children's self-service and household work (cleaning clothes and shoes, simple repair of toys, books, clothes, restoring order in the group and on the kindergarten site, in their room, helping parents in cleaning the apartment, cooking simple dishes with adults, caring for plants and animals). It is advisable to include children both in separate work processes (dusting, washing doll clothes, watering plants) and holistic types of work (group cleaning, duty in a corner of nature).

In addition, it is necessary to design the inclusion of all pupils in everyday work in kindergarten conditions. To develop the ability to plan work, to clearly talk about the main stages of the implementation of the plan, to agree on the distribution of responsibilities in a small group of peers, distributing work according to the method of common and joint work.

DISCUSSION

Directing plot-role-playing games, the educator creates conditions for the inclusion of labor processes with real tools in the game conditional plot (sewing clothes for dolls, crafts made of paper, wood and other materials). At the same time, it is necessary to widely practice techniques that encourage the creative development of the idea, the search for the material necessary for its implementation (children's experimentation, the simplest operational maps).

In the preparatory group, it is necessary to orient children to help adults as much as possible in household work, consistently expanding the range of assignments (wiping dust on shelves with toys, from window sills, on furniture in the bedroom, putting things in order in the utility closet, etc.). To develop children's skills to consciously accept a task from an adult or set it independently, the ability to choose the best solution, try to find options on your own, get advice, additional information from an adult, evaluate your capabilities, ask for help if necessary, control yourself, showing strong-willed efforts to achieve a high-quality result of work.

It is important to take into account the preferences of girls and boys for different types of productive activities: beading, cross-stitch, crocheting, sewing doll clothes and soft toys, crafts made of paper, wood, constructors, junk and natural material. For these purposes, it is acceptable to organize children's mini-workshops, creative studios, interest groups. In the context of the search for different forms of organization of the pedagogical process

, the use of children's leisure is relevant.

In the research of M. V. Krulekht and A. A. Krulekht, the program "Samodelkino" and the pedagogical technology of organizing leisure activities of boys 5-6 years old associated with the construction of waste material were developed. The authors, following many researchers (I. Ya. Bazik, R. S. Bure, E. K. Gulyants, O. V. Dybina, T. A. Markova, F. P. Filenko, etc.) attribute the construction of waste material to manual labor. Therefore, in the proposed technology, it is considered in the logic of the structure of the labor process: the goal (creation of crafts, project implementation), waste material for labor, tools, labor actions to create crafts, the craft itself or the project as a result of labor (V. I. Loginova) [38].

If the construction is used in the organization of children's leisure, then it is possible to implement creative projects with its help. Project topics ("Space travel", "Design Bureau", "From carriage to rocket", "City of the Future", "Knight's Castle", "Gift to Mom") are presented to children in the form of a design task, for example, it is necessary to decide what will be required for space travel, what can be done, who will do etc.

The proposed content of children's leisure activities allows us to take into account the uniqueness of the subculture of the modern senior preschooler, compliance with age and gender

interests and inclinations of boys and girls 5-6 years old. The proposed technologies of labor education of preschoolers contribute not only to the development of the child's diligence, the ability to apply intellectual and physical efforts to achieve the desired result, but also to the strengthening of the children's community, friendly relationships, the formation of a specific children's subculture.

The history of the formation of the methodology for the development of elementary mathematical concepts in preschool age. The methodology of the development of mathematical representations in children is a relatively young scientific pedagogical discipline. A historical digression shows how views on the initial teaching of mathematics to children gradually changed depending on the needs of life, the level of development of mathematical science and teaching methods at school.

The basis of the methodology was oral folk art: a variety of fairy tales, counting books, sayings, proverbs, riddles, jokes, etc. The first stage of the development of the methodology is empirical (XVIII—XIX centuries). The issues of the content and methods of teaching preschool children arithmetic and the development of ideas about sizes, measures, time and space are reflected in the advanced pedagogical systems of education developed by Ya. A. Komensky, I. G. Pestalozzi, K. D. Ushinsky, L. N. Tolstoy, etc[39-40]

Advanced ideas in teaching arithmetic to children before school were expressed by the Russian democratic teacher, the founder of scientific pedagogy in Russia, K. D. Ushinsky (1824-1870). He proposed to teach children the counting of individual subjects and groups, the actions of addition and subtraction, to form an understanding of the ten as a unit of account.

The writer and teacher L. N. Tolstoy published *The ABC* in 1872, one of the parts of which is *The Account*. Criticizing the existing teaching methods, L. N. Tolstoy proposed to teach children to count "forward" and "backward" within a hundred, to study numbering, based on children's practical experience gained in the game.

Advanced teachers of the past, Russian and foreign, recognized the role and necessity of primary mathematical knowledge in the development and upbringing of children before school, allocated an account as a means of mental development and recommended teaching children it from about 3 years old. Learning was understood by them as "exercise" in performing practical, playful actions using visual material.

The second stage of the development of the methodology falls on the 1920s-1950s. During these years, the problems of selecting the content, methods of developing mathematical representations in children were discussed in order to prepare them for mastering mathematics at school. E. I. Tikheeva, L. V. Glagoleva, F. N. Bleher and others developed methodological manuals, programs, games and didactic materials that contribute to the mathematical development of preschoolers.

The position of E. I. Tikheeva is revealed and justified in the "natural" way of children's development in the field of mathematics proposed by her. She understood the "natural" path of development as the only one leading to the normal development of numerical and mathematical representations in children in general: corresponding to age and individual capabilities, the needs of each child, the current situation and the interest in comparison, measurement, counting, compilation of arithmetic examples and tasks, division of the subject into fractions.

The "natural" path of a child's development in the field of mathematics proceeds in amateur activity, which was understood as the active participation of a child in everything that

interests him.

The games-classes developed by E. I. Tikheeva implemented a program created by her for the development of mathematical concepts in children and the requirements of vitality, reality in teaching children.

Until 1939, in Leningrad kindergartens, children were taught numeracy according to the methods of L.V.Glagoleva and F.N.Blecher. In a number of methodological manuals by L. V. Glagoleva (researcher, methodologist, practitioner) — "Teaching arithmetic by laboratory method" (1919), "Comparison of the values of subjects in zero groups of schools" (1930), "Mathematics in zero groups" (1930) — the content, methods and techniques for the development of children's initial ideas about numbers, quantities and their measurement, dividing the whole into equal parts.

The main ideas about the content and methods of teaching are set forth by F. N. Blecher (1895-1977) in the book "Mathematics in kindergarten and the zero group" (1934), which became the first textbook and program for higher and secondary educational institutions to train educators for the Soviet kindergarten.

The program of teaching children to count, developed by F. N. Blecher, used data from foreign psychologists, their own observations about the time and timing of the child's perception of different numbers[37-38].

F. N. Blecher has developed not only the content of teaching children, but also methods, mainly gaming. The system of didactic games created by her to this day in preschool institutions serves the development of mathematical concepts and mental abilities of children. According to F. N. Blecher, didactic games, although they are one of the important teaching methods, still cannot replace its other forms and methods.

Based on the analysis of theoretical and methodological publications by F. N. Blecher, it can be concluded that she created the first didactic system of teaching mathematics in our country in preschool institutions.

The third stage of the development of the methodology is the 1950s and 1960s. During these years, the issues of the development of mathematical representations in preschool children were developed by A.M. Leushina (1898-1982) since the 1950s. Thanks to her work, the methodology of the development of mathematical representations in children received theoretical, scientific, psychological and pedagogical justification, the patterns of the development of quantitative representations in children in conditions of purposeful learning in kindergarten classes were revealed.

A.M. Leushina laid the foundations of a didactic system for the formation of mathematical representations, creating a program, content, methods and techniques for working with children from 3 to 6 years old. The theoretical and methodological concept of the author is as follows: from the undifferentiated perception of sets of objects, children must be translated to the identification of individual constituent elements by pairwise comparison, which represents a numerical learning period (assimilation of the relations "as much", "equally", "more", "less", etc.).

Learning to count is based on the development of children's actions with sets and is based on the comparison of two sets. Children get acquainted with the number as a characteristic of the number of a specific subject group (set) in comparison with another. In further comparison of numbers (on a visual basis), the child learns the sequence and the relationship between them,

which leads to the conscious development of counting and its use in calculations, performing actions when solving simple arithmetic problems. An elementary idea of number is formed in children during the accumulation of their experience of comparing several subject groups on the basis of quantity independently of others (qualitative features, location in space). On this basis, the development of quantitative and ordinal counting was built, the determination of the composition of numbers from ones and two smaller numbers.

The concept developed by A.M. Leushina in the 60-70s was significantly supplemented by scientific, theoretical and methodological development of the problem of the development of spatial-temporal representations in preschoolers. The results of scientific research are reflected in her doctoral dissertation "Preparing children for the assimilation of arithmetic material at school" (1956), numerous publications, textbooks: "Teaching numeracy in kindergarten" (Moscow, 1959; 1961), "Formation of elementary mathematical representations in preschool children" (Moscow, 1974).

Modern technologies of logical and mathematical development of preschool children. The development and choice of technologies depend primarily on what is to be mastered (content) and what the development of the child's mental activity will consist of. It is necessary to highlight the content, the development of which ensures the activity of cognitive actions (practical and mental), the child's recognition of connections and dependencies of objects and phenomena of the surrounding world.

CONCLUSION

This is the development of the properties of objects, such as shape, size, mass, capacity; methods for evaluating discrete and continuous quantities through comparison, counting, measurement, establishing relationships and dependencies of individual objects and groups according to different properties, orientation in schemes and models.

The development of a child's mental activity is determined by the development of his skills to choose and carry out activities using active search (research) actions, correlate them with the result, strive for the ultimate goal based on forecasting (and if so, then ...), objectively evaluate the result by comparing it with his own attitude (goal).

The technology of mathematical development, in the implementation of which a child strives for active activity, and an adult expects a positive, original creative result from him, is a problem game. In the process of using this technology, the child is not limited in independent search for practical actions, experimentation, communication with adults and peers about the course of the situation, resolution of contradictions and mistakes, manifestations of joy and sorrow, and other intellectual emotions.

The method of mastering games is connected with the fact that an adult engages a child in a new game, encouraging him to be active, at the same time observing how he perceives the essence of the game, whether he owns the actions of comparison, generalization, counting, measurement, classification and others; the ability to establish connections and dependencies of individual objects and groups of objects in shape, size, spatial location.

As the development of games together with an adult and in individual activities, the child proceeds to participate in them at a higher level. These are, as a rule, newly emerging games with adults or children successfully playing them. The difference from games at an earlier stage is the introduction of changes in the plot by the child, the manifestation of creative elements, the transformation of the search for answers, a brighter emotional saturation of the game[17].

Conditionally, three stages can be distinguished in the development of games by a child: 1) games with adults and peers (joint); 2) games at the level of amateur activity; 3) games with adults and peers at a higher level (compared to the first stage).

Problem situations are considered not only as a means of activating thinking, but also as a means of mastering search actions, the ability to formulate one's own thoughts about search methods and the intended result.

The structural components of a problematic situation are problematic issues, actions (search and research). An adult can ask such questions: "How to cut a square into triangles? How many different ways can you offer?", "If you swap the numbers 2 and 8, what will change? Is it possible to use the digit 2 in the value of 8 (as 8)?"

Problem situations for preschool children include entertaining tasks, questions, joke tasks and other types of non-standard mathematical material, the search for answers to which proceeds actively, based on visibility. For example: "There are three pencils of different lengths on the table. How to remove the longest pencil from the middle without touching it?" This task can become part of a problematic situation about the dependence of the qualitative characteristics of objects on their spatial location[15].

One of the means of technology aimed at accumulating logical and mathematical experience is educational developing situations. They are characterized by a game orientation of activity, saturation with problematic and creative tasks, the presence of search situations with elements of experimentation, practical research, schematization. E. A. Nosova has developed a complex of game developing situations with logical blocks of Dienes, in which children master logical dependencies: identification and abstraction of properties of objects (color, shape, size, thickness), comparison, classification and generalization, as well as logical actions and mental operations.

In educational situations, children master the means and methods of cognition (sensory and measuring standards, speech, models, comparison, counting and generalization, measurement, classification and serialization), appropriate terminology, logical connections, dependencies and the ability to express them in the form of simple logical statements, the ability to act on the instructions of the teacher, sample, rules and algorithms, own design.

An educational situation may consist of a plot-plot, definition of actors, sequence in the development of the storyline, actions of schematization, transformation, etc..

This is undoubtedly an innovative stage in the development of higher professional pedagogical education in our country.

The professional activity of a modern teacher of preschool education — an activity focused on the holistic development and upbringing of a child in the pedagogical process — requires a special, new quality of teacher training.

The innovativeness of this training system is determined by:

firstly, ensuring the conditions of continuity of education, the possibility of building a professional career on the basis of obtaining educational degrees - bachelor's and master's;

secondly, ensuring the unity of the target, content and technological components of the educational process, focused on the quality of training, the indicator of which is the professional competence of the future teacher.

The competence-based approach to the analysis of professional activity and, in general, a person's education is becoming the leading one in the modern social system.

The idea of our textbook is based on the logic of the competence approach, which presupposes the formation of pedagogical competence among future teachers as a readiness to solve the leading groups of tasks of professional activity: diagnostic, design, self-education tasks, tasks of interaction with the subjects of the pedagogical process.

Conclusions about the views of children in the block "I and the world around me" are related to the fact that a modern child has a variety and breadth of views on the world. Social orientation in the life of a child allows him to understand the world around him well by the age of six, to understand his identity and diversity. Children want to study at school, understand that education is closely linked to their future, knowledge is necessary for work.

Education for a modern preschooler has an applied nature, which reflects the trivial, everyday views on education of most people in society. Children of Russian cities show a good orientation in the world of material values, the computer, toys, telephone and TV become important for them. There is a huge diversity in the children's subculture, today it is wider than the traditional classification of the content of the subculture of preschoolers proposed by adults. The "secret world" of childhood has been significantly updated, it needs to be studied more carefully and in more detail in order to correctly interpret and understand.

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